

A REVIEW ON *GUNA SIDDHANTA*: AN INSIGHT INTO *GHRITA PRAYOGA* IN *GULMA*

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ABSTRACT

Gulma is one of the eight diseases described in *Nidana Sthana* of *Caraka samhita* characterized by a symptom complex that includes complaints such as *Shoola* (pain) and formation of a *Granthi* (lump). A clearer insight into *Gulma* is essential to effectively utilize the textual descriptions of this obscure disease and its treatment in clinical practice. Hence, a detailed analysis of the Ayurvedic description of *Gulma Samprapti* and importance of *Ghrita Prayoga* is presented here based on *Guna siddhanta* along with its treatment principles.

KEY WORDS: *Gulma*, *Guna siddhanta*, *Samprapti*, *Ghrita prayoga*.

INTRODUCTION

Guna is one among *Shadkarana*, and plays an important role in *Chikitsa* to achieve the ultimate goal of Ayurveda (*Karya*) i.e. *Dhatusamyata*. *Guna Siddhanta* refers to the principles related to qualities or attributes that define substances, objects, or concepts in various Indian philosophies. These *Gunas* are present in every *Aushadha Dravya* as well as in *Shareera*. Since, *Guna* is inseparably related to *Dravya* and are present in *Aushadhi dravya*, when they come into contact with *Shareera*, they get disintegrated into their *Gunas* with the help of *Agni* and they act on particular *Dosha*

possessing similar *Guna*. Among them, *Gurvadi Guna* hold significant importance due to its pharmacological and therapeutic application. Even when *Dosha* and *Dushya* are constant, *Guna-visheshata* alters the pathological nature and therapeutic requirement of the disease. Each *Dosha* is composed of specific *Gunas* and the manifestation of disease is often influenced not just by the *Dosha* itself but by the dominance of particular *Gunas*. Thus, *Guna* is a crucial component of *Chikitsa*. Ayurvedic treatments are based on balancing these *Gunas* to maintain health and treat diseases effectively.

Since *Gulma* is primarily associated with *Vata dosha* (though it may have involvement of *Pitta* and *Kapha* in different types), the selection of treatment is based on opposing *Gunas* to counteract the aggravated *Dosha* and its manifestations.

Objectives

1. To analyse the concept of *Gulma Samprapti* with a special focus to *Guna siddhanta*.
2. To evaluate the therapeutic application of *Ghrita prayoga* in management of *Gulma*, based on the principles of *Guna siddhanta*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This conceptual study is based on a comprehensive literature review of classical Ayurvedic texts. It aims to establish a systematic understanding of the *Guna* involved in *Gulma* and their collective influence on its treatment. The gathered information is critically analysed, leading to a structured discussion. Based on this analysis, relevant conclusions were drawn regarding the therapeutic application of *Guna Siddhanta* in the management of *Gulma*.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Nirukti and Definition of *Gulma*

The word '*Gulma*' is derived from the root word '*Gud dhatu*' which refers to any growth in the body that resembles a bush.^[1] It is defined as a round shaped *Granthi* (lump) that develops between the *Hridaya* (heart) and *Basti* (bladder). This lump may be movable or immovable, sometimes increasing in size and sometimes subsiding and localises in five specific *Sthanas* i.e. *Hridaya*, *Nabhi*, *Parshwa*, *Udara*, *Basti*.^[2]

Nidana^[3]

In *Vatala Prakriti* individuals emaciated by *Jwara*, *Vamana*, *Virechana*, *Atisara* and various etiological factors which aggravate *Vata dosha*, such as intake of *Vatala Ahara*, cold

regimens, procedures without proper *Snehana*, suppression of natural urges, excessive water intake, physical exertion, emaciated, reduced nourishment to *Dhatus*, alcohol, grief, and trauma cause *Vata Prakopa*. *Vata* along with *Pitta* is further vitiated by sour, salty, pungent, alkaline, and hot foods, eating before digestion, exposure to wind and sun, and consuming unctuous, heavy, sweet, and cold foods in excess. *Vata* along with *Kapha* further gets vitiated by substances like sugarcane, milk, sesame, jaggery, alcohol, and marshy animal meat, along with lifestyle errors like urge suppression and over drinking without appetite, also disturbs the normal functioning of *Vata*.

Samprapti

The aggravated *Vata* enters the *Mahasrotas*, causing dryness and hardening, localizes in the *Koshta* (*Hridaya*, *Basti*, *Parshwa*, *Nabhi*), and produces pain (*Shoola*) and lump-like masses (*Gulma*) with a compact, rounded form.^[4]

Lakshana^[5]

The *Pinda* predominant with *Vata Dosha* fluctuates in size due to *Vata's Chala Guna*, causing irregular pain- sometimes acute, sometimes mild. Symptoms include piercing, twitching, splitting pain, tingling, numbness, muscle contraction, and a crawling sensation like ants on the limbs. Additional features are evening fever, dry mouth, breath obstruction, and horripilation during pain episodes.

In case of *Pittaja Gulma*, there is a burning sensation in the abdomen, heart region, chest, and throat. The person feels as if smoke is coming out, as they expel sour eructation along with a sensation of internal heat. The area around the *Gulma* feels as if it is burning, paining, being fumigated, heated, and sweating. The body becomes moist, heavy, and feels loosened, with tenderness to touch, accompanied by slight horripilation.

Kaphaja Gulma presents with cold fever, loss of appetite, indigestion, body ache, horripilation, vomiting, drowsiness, lethargy, heaviness, and burning sensation in the head. The *Gulma* is stable, heavy, hard, and deeply seated, with persistent numbness. When aggravated, it causes cough, breathing difficulty, nasal congestion, and paleness of the skin, nails, eyes, face, urine, and stool.

Vataja Gulma Chikitsa^[6]

In the management of *Gulma*, if the condition is caused by dryness (*Rukshata*) due to excessive physical exertion (*Vyayama*), and is associated with severe pain (*Teevra Vedana*) as well as obstruction to faeces and flatus (*Baddha Vit-Maruta*), *Snehana* therapy should be administered. This includes the application of unctuous substances through diet (*Anna*), external application (*Abhyanga*), internal consumption (*Paana*), enemas (*Niruha* and *Anuvasana*), effectively utilizing all four methods of oleation.

Following proper *Snehana*, *Swedana* (sudation therapy) should be given, as it helps to soften the bodily channels), pacify the aggravated *Vata*, and relieve the obstruction.^[9] *Snehapana* is particularly beneficial when *Gulma* is situated above the umbilical region. If *Gulma* is located in *Pakwashaya* or *Jatara*, both types of *Basti* - *Niruha* and *Anuvasana* should be administered. When the disease resides in the regions around the umbilicus (*Nabhigata*) or its sides (*Nabhi Parshvagata*), *Basti* becomes crucial. For patients with *Vataja Gulma* accompanied by obstruction to flatus and faeces (*Vibandha*), once *Agni* is stimulated, *Brimhana Anna-Pana* along with unctuous and warm drinks (*Snigdha-Ushna Pana*) are recommended. Frequent administration of *Snehana* in the forms of *Paana*, *Niruha*, and *Anuvasana* is advisable, but caution must be exercised to prevent aggravation of *Kapha* and *Pitta Doshas*.

Pittaja Gulma Chikitsa^[7]

In the case of *Pittaja Gulma* caused by unctuous (*Snigdha*) and hot (*Ushna*) substances, *Sramsana* (mild purgation) is advised. When *Gulma* arises from dryness (*Ruksha*) and heat (*Ushna*), the use of *Sarpi* (medicated ghee) is beneficial. If *Pitta* or *Pittaja Gulma* becomes lodged in *Pakwashaya*, administering *Tikta-Ksheera Basti* (enema of milk processed with bitter drugs) is recommended. *Virechana* (purgation) should be done using milk boiled with bitter herbs (*Tikta Paya*) or *Tilvaka Ghrita*. When *Gulma* is accompanied by symptoms like thirst, fever, burning sensation, pain, sweating, reduced digestive power, and loss of appetite, *Raktamokshana* (bloodletting) becomes essential, as the blood becomes vitiated and sour in this condition. Removing the vitiated blood prevents further complications and relieves the patient from pain, as vitiated blood is considered the root cause of *Gulma*. Post *Raktamokshana*, the patient now emaciated, should be nourished with the soup of *Jangala mamsa*, and medicated ghee to alleviate any remaining pain. If *Rakta* and *Pitta* are severely

aggravated and *Raktamokshana* is not performed adequately, the *Gulma* may suppurate, necessitating surgical intervention (*Shastra Karma*).

Kaphaja Gulma Chikitsa^[8]

In *Kaphaja Gulma*, *Langhana* (fasting) is recommended when caused by cold, heavy, or unctuous foods, especially if the patient has weak digestion or is unfit for *Vamana*. *Vamana* is advised for low digestive power, abdominal pain, heaviness, stiffness in the abdomen, nausea, and loss of appetite. Following these therapies, a hot diet with pungent (*Katu*) and bitter (*Tikta*) tastes is prescribed to restore digestive balance. For abdominal distension, obstruction, or hard, elevated *Gulma*, treatment begins with *Swedana* (sudation) and *Vilayana* (massage) to soften the mass. After *Swedana* and *Vamana*, *Ghrita Pana* with *Kshara-Katu Siddha Ghrita* enhances digestion. Once the mass loosens, *Virechana* and *Basti* are given. If *Agni Mandhya* and *Muda Vata* persist, formulations like *Gutika*, *Choorna*, and *Niryuha* are used. For deep-seated and hard *Gulma*, *Kshara-Arishta* and *Agnikarma* are recommended.

Kshara should be given after assessing the dominance of *Kapha*, the patient's constitution, season (*Hemanta* or *Shishira*), and strength of the disease. It should be repeated every one to three days based on the patient's strength, supported with meat, milk, and ghee for nourishment. *Kshara* has an erosive property (*Ksharana*), helping to break down *Kaphaja Gulma*, enhance body strength, and eliminate the vitiated *Dosha*.

If the patient suffers from poor appetite and indigestion, *Arishta* should be used to purify the body channels (*Marga Shuddhi*). If *Gulma* remains even after these therapies due to its deep-rooted nature, *Daha Karma* (cauterization) with sharp instruments like *Shara* or *Loha* should be done after *Raktamokshana*. This works through its heat (*Ushnata*) and sharpness (*Teekshnata*), pacifying *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha* and disintegrating the compact mass.

Dwandaja Gulma Chikitsa

In *Vataja Gulma* with aggravated *Kapha*, symptoms like *Agnimandya*, nausea, heaviness, and drowsiness are managed with *Vamana*. For combined *Vata-Kapha Gulma* with pain, distension, and obstruction, remedies like *Varti Prayoga*, *Gutika*, and *Choorna* that balance both *Doshas* are effective. If *Pitta* is involved, causing burning and heat, *Virechana* with unctuous *Anulomaka* drugs is advised. When *Gulma* persists despite treatment, *Raktamokshana* with *Shringa* instruments helps eliminate the residual pathology.

Atyayika chikitsa

If the patient of *Vata Gulma* has symptoms like colic pain, *Anaha* (abdominal distension) and constipation, then he should be given fomentation therapy with the help of *Nadi*, *Prastara* or *Sankhara* type of fomentation. Medicated enema is the best therapy for curing *Gulma*. In the beginning, it overcomes *Vata* in its own site, and thus, immediately overcomes *Gulma*. Therefore, *Niruha* and *Anuvasana* types of *Basti* has to be administered. If *Pittaja Gulma* is in its acute stage, then one should administer ghee processed with purgative drugs or bitter drugs like *Rohinyadi ghrta*.

Avasthanusara chikitsa

Snehana

If *Gulma* arises from *Rukshata* with severe pain and obstruction of faeces and flatus, *Snehapana* (*Sarpi*, *Taila*, *Vasa*, *Majja*) is recommended. *Snehana dravyas*, possessing *Guru-Snigdha-Sukshma-Mrudu-Manda-Picchila* properties, counteract *Vata dosha* by restoring moisture and softness. This therapy alleviates aggravated *Vata*, softens the body, and disintegrates *Mala*.

Swedana

Swedana (sudation therapy) is a vital Ayurvedic treatment, especially for *Vataja Gulma*, as it softens body channels (*Srotas*), alleviates pain, bloating, and obstruction (*Sangha*). It liquefies and expels vitiated *Doshas* (*Vata*) while relieving stiffness (*Stambha*) and heaviness (*Gourava*) by its qualities like hot, sharp, mobile, and unctuous (*Ushna-Teekshna-Sara-Snigdha*). If the *Gulma* is *Katina* and *Unnata* (elevated), brings *Vilayana* of *Dosha* due to its *Ushna*, *Teekshna* and *Sukshma* properties.

Basti

Basti is effective, particularly when *Gulma* located in the *Pakwashaya* (colon) or *Jatara* (abdomen), as these are primary sites of *Vata*. It counteracts *Vata*'s inherent dryness, lightness, and coldness (*Ruksha*, *Laghu*, *Sheeta*) with the unctuous, heavy, and warm properties (*Snigdha*, *Guru*, *Ushna*) of medicated oils and decoctions. This helps in softening obstructions, restoring normal movement, and eliminating accumulated waste. *Tikta Ksheera Basti* is effective in *Pittaja Gulma* as it pacifies *Pitta* while nourishing *Vata*. According to *Guna Siddhanta*, milk's cooling, unctuous, and stabilizing properties counteract *Pitta*'s heat, while bitter herbs aid detoxification and bile regulation. This therapy reduces inflammation,

soothes the intestines, eliminates toxins, and softens abdominal masses, making it essential for restoring balance in *Pittaja Gulma*.

Brimhana

Brimhana therapy is beneficial in *Vataja Gulma*, when accompanied by constipation (*Vibandha*) and dryness (*Rukshata*) in the body. According to *Guna Siddhanta*, *Brimhana* substances possess heavy (*Guru*), unctuous (*Snigdha*), soft (*Mridu*), and stable (*Sthira*) properties, which effectively counteract the lightness (*Laghu*), dryness (*Ruksha*), instability (*Chala*) of aggravated *Vata* and promoting overall tissue growth.

Raktamokshana

Raktamokshana is an effective due to its ability to alleviate pain (*Vedanahara*) and reduce the excessive subtlety (*Sukshmata*) of *Vata*. According to *Guna Siddhanta*, it lightens the body, relieves congestion, and removes vitiated blood, which in turn helps balance *Vata* and in reducing pain, especially when associated with *Vata* and *Rakta* vitiation.

Sramsana

Sramsana is a form of *Virechana* (purgation therapy), used in *Pittaja Gulma* caused by excessive intake of unctuous (*Snigdha*) and hot (*Ushna*). It enhances lightness (*Laghu*), sharpness (*Teekshna*), and mobility of bodily substances (*Sara*), liquefying and expelling accumulated waste (*Mala*) and excess *Pitta*. By regulating digestion and clearing obstruction, *Sramsana* reduces inflammation, restores balance, and prevents further *Pitta* aggravation.

Virechana

Virechana (purgation therapy) with *Tikta Ghrita* helps eliminate excess *Pitta* from the body. *Virechana* drugs possess hot (*Ushna*), sharp (*Teekshna*), subtle (*Sukshma*), and spreading properties (*Vyavayi*), which help in penetrating deep tissues, liquefying and expelling accumulated *Pitta* toxins through the intestines. The addition of *Tikta Ghrita* enhances cooling and detoxifying effects, preventing excessive dryness while balancing both *Pitta* and *Vata*.

Raktamokshana

Raktamokshana (bloodletting therapy) is highly beneficial in *Pittaja Gulma*, especially when symptoms like thirst (*Trishna*), fever (*Jwara*), burning sensation (*Daha*), pain (*Shoola*), and excessive sweating (*Sweda*) are present. As *Pitta* and *Rakta* share hot (*Ushna*) and sharp

(*Teekshna*) qualities, leads to blood vitiation and *Amla Bhava* in *Gulma*. *Raktamokshana* reduces pain and inflammation by detoxifying circulation.

Langhana

Langhana effectively reduces *Kapha* dominance in *Kaphaja Gulma* by its light (*Laghu*), hot (*Ushna*), sharp (*Teekshna*), and dry (*Ruksha*) properties, which counteract *Kapha*'s heaviness and stagnation. It enhances digestion, clears obstructions, and promotes elimination, helping to reduce *Gulma* size and alleviate symptoms like heaviness and indigestion.

Vamana

Vamana (emesis therapy) is effective in *Kaphaja Gulma*, as it utilizes hot (*Ushna*), sharp (*Teekshna*), subtle (*Sukshma*), and spreading properties to liquefy and expel *Kapha*. By clearing obstructions and reducing heaviness, *Vamana* restores digestive fire (*Agni*), improves metabolism, and prevents further *Kapha* accumulation.

Ushna Prayoga

Due to its hot (*Ushna*), sharp (*Teekshna*), penetrating (*Sukshma*), and mobile (*Chala*) qualities, helps in liquefying and mobilizing accumulated *Kapha*, clearing obstructions, and enhancing digestion. By stimulating metabolism and reducing congestion, *Ushna Prayoga* alleviates heaviness, indigestion, and stiffness, making it effective in the treatment of *Kaphaja Gulma*.

Kshara Prayoga

Kshara (alkaline therapy), particularly when it is deep-seated, large, hard, immobile, and heavy. *Kshara* possesses hot (*Ushna*), sharp (*Teekshna*), penetrating (*Sukshma*), corrosive, and drying properties, which help in gradually eroding and breaking down the dense *Kapha* accumulation. Its *Lekhana* (scraping), *Shodhana* (purifying), and *Pachana* (digestive) actions aid in reducing mass, clearing obstructions, and enhancing metabolism.

Arishta Prayoga

Arishta (fermented Ayurvedic preparations) aids in *Kaphaja Gulma*, by clearing obstructions and enhancing digestion. According to *Guna Siddhanta*, it's hot (*Ushna*), subtle (*Sukshma*), and sharp (*Teekshna*) properties, stimulate *Agni*, liquefy *Kapha*, and clear *Srotas*. This improves metabolism, reduces heaviness, and restores physiological balance.

Daha Karma

Daha Karma is effective for *Kaphaja Gulma*, breaking down dense *Kapha* formations. Its hot, sharp, and fast-acting properties penetrate tissues, liquefy obstructions, and dissolve *Gulma*. By generating heat and improving circulation, it restores metabolism and relieves stiffness.

Sarpi prayoga

Sarpi Prayoga, or the use of medicated ghee, is highly effective in *Pittaja Gulma*, especially when caused by dry (*Ruksha*) and hot (*Ushna*) factors. *Ghee* possesses cooling (*Sheeta*), softening (*Mridu*), and unctuous (*Snigdha*) properties, which help in pacifying both *Pitta* and *Vata* by counteracting their heat and dryness. It nourishes and strengthens vital tissues like *Rasa*, *Shukra*, and *Ojas*. *Ghrita*, though generally unctuous and cooling, can be beneficial in *Kaphaja Gulma* when processed with *Tikta* (bitter) or *Ushna* (hot) herbs. Its subtle and penetrating nature helps clear blockages, improve digestion, and regulate *Kapha* without excessive mucus formation, making it useful in specific cases of *Kaphaja Gulma*.

Action of *Ghrita Prayoga* in *Gulma*^[9] based on *Guna Siddhanta*

Ghrita Prayoga (medicated ghee therapy) plays a significant role in its management due to its deep-penetrative, rejuvenating, digestive properties.

Vata-Pitta Shamana (Pacifying *Vata* and *Pitta Dosha*): *Ghrita* counteracts *Vata* in *Gulma* with its *Snigdha*, *Guru*, and *Manda* properties, relieving dryness, bloating, pain, and irregular digestion. Example: *Dashamoola Ghrita* is useful in *Vataja Gulma* due to its strong *Vata* suppressing action.

Beneficial for *Rasadi dhatu* and *Ojas*: *Ghrita*, as a *Rasayana*, nourishes *Rasaadi Dhatu* in *Agni Mandya*. Its *Guru* and *Yogavahi* properties support deep tissue nourishment and prevent degeneration.

Brings *Mriduta*: *Ghrita's Mridu* and *Sukshma* properties soften hardened *Mahasrotas*, reducing *Gulma's* rigidity. It alleviates obstruction by breaking down accumulated masses, fibrotic tissue, and hardened stool, restoring normal bowel movement.

Deepana-Pachana: *Ghrita* enhances digestion by stimulating *Agni* (digestive fire) and removing *Ama* (toxins) that contribute to *Gulma* formation. Example: *Panchatikta Ghrita*,

Trikatu Ghrita, and *Hingwadi Ghrita* help improve digestion and reduce abdominal distension.

Sheeta Guna: Pacifies *Pitta Dosha*, which is often involved in inflammation, hyperacidity, and ulcer-like symptoms in *Pittaja Gulma*. *Sheeta guna* of *Ghrita* helps to alleviate these symptoms.

Yogavahi: Enhances the potency of herbs it is processed with, making medicated ghee formulations highly effective in *Gulma Chikitsa*.

Pharmacological action of *Ghrita*

Ghee contains about 8% fewer saturated fatty acids, making it easier to digest, with a high absorption rate of 96%. Its lipophilic properties aid in transporting active ingredients to target organs and facilitating cellular absorption. Additionally, the fatty acids in ghee support digestion and gut health.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This article focuses on role of *Gunas* of *Vata Dosha* in *Gulma Chikitsa* starting from the *Nidana panchaka* to treatment principles, various formulations as well as dietary regimens.

In the *Samprapti* of *Gulma*, it is fundamentally a *Vata pradhana Tridoshaja Vyadhi* where the vitiation of *Vata Dosha* occurs especially involving *Ruksha* (dry), *Laghu* (light), *Sheeta* (cold), *Khara* (rough), *Chala* (mobile), and *Sukshma* (subtle) *Gunas*. When these *Gunas* become excessive, they show various *Lakshanas* based on the predominance of *Doshas*. *Acharya Caraka* emphasizes that even when *Vata* is the primary *Dosha*, the *Guna Vishesha Siddhanta* determine the type, severity, and treatment approach of *Gulma*. Hence, treatment aims at employing substances and procedures with the *Gunas* which encounters the aggravated *Vata*.

Swedana with *Ushna*, *Teekshna*, *Sara*, *Snigdha Gunas* softens the channels and liquefies obstructed *Doshas*. It counterbalances *Vata's Sheeta* and *Ruksha Gunas*, hence relieves stiffness (*Stambha*) and pain (*Shoola*), and prepares the body for *Snehana* and *Basti*. The combination of *Snehana* and *Swedana* embodies the *Guna* based synergy, ensuring comprehensive pacification of *Vata*.

Basti is the prime therapy for *Vata* disorders. *Caraka* specifies *Niruha* and *Anuvasana Basti* using decoctions and oils with *Snigdha*, *Guru*, and *Ushna Gunas* to alleviate *Ruksha* and *Sheeta* qualities of *Vata*. *Tikta-Ksheera Basti* for *Pitta-Vata Gulma* uses the *Sheeta* and *Snigdha* property of milk and *Tikta* herbs to balance both *Doshas*. *Sneha Basti* restores moisture and reduces dryness in the *Mahasrotas*. Thus, *Basti Chikitsa* directly reverses the pathological *Gunas* of *Vata* and reestablishes its normal functioning.

Focusing on *Pathya* and *Apathya* in *Vataja Gulma*, the vitiated *Vata* is dominated by *Ruksha* (dryness), *Sheeta* (coldness), *Laghu* (lightness), and *Khara* (roughness). Therefore, *Pathya Ahara* and *Vihara* should embody the opposite qualities i.e. *Snigdha* (unctuousness), *Ushna* (warmth), *Guru* (heaviness), and *Mridu* (softness) in order to pacify *Vata* through *Guna-viparita Chikitsa*. Substances having *Ruksha*, *Sheeta*, *Laghu*, and *Khara Gunas* and *Ati Vyayama- Upavasa* aggravate the *Vata* worsening the *Rukshata* of *Vyadhi*.

Ghrita Prayoga, based on *Guna Siddhanta*, manages *Gulma* through its *Snigdha*, *Guru*, *Manda*, and *Sheeta* properties that pacify *Vata* and *Pitta*, relieve pain, and ease digestion. Acting as a *Rasayana*, it nourishes *Dhatus*, enhances *Ojas*, softens hardened masses, and clears obstructions. Its *Deepana-Pachana* and *Yogavahi* actions improve digestion and enhance the efficacy of herbs, making it highly effective in *Gulma Chikitsa*. Around 14 *Ghrita* preparations like *Tryushanadi ghrita*, *Hingu souvarchalaadi ghrita*, *Hapushadi ghrita*, *Pippalyadi ghrita*, *Neelinyadi ghrita*, *Rohinyadi ghrita*, *Vasa ghrita*, *Drakshadi ghrita*, *Ksheera shatpalaka ghrita*, etc has been indicated in various conditions of *Gulma* as it plays a significant role in its management due to its deep-penetrative, rejuvenating, digestive properties.

The Role of *Guna Siddhanta* in *Gulma*

The fundamental principle of *Guna Siddhanta* in *Gulma Chikitsa* is based on treating the disease by counteracting the predominant *Gunas* responsible for its manifestation. Treatment principles focus on administering *Dravyas* (substances) that possess opposing *Gunas* to restore balance.

Table No 1: Understanding the Dosha Gunas in Gulma.

Vataja	Pittaja	Kaphaja	Raktaja
<p><i>Ruksha</i> (dryness) due to aggravated <i>Vata</i>. <i>Laghu</i> (lightness) increases instability and dryness. <i>Khara</i> (roughness) leads to stiffness and obstruction. <i>Sheeta</i> (coldness) causes constriction and pain. <i>Sukshma</i> (subtlety) penetrates deep into tissues and causes discomfort. <i>Vishada</i> (non-slimy) enhances dryness and obstruction.</p>	<p><i>Ushna</i> (hot) causes burning sensation. <i>Teekshna</i>(sharp) leads to severe pain. <i>Drava</i>(liquid) Enhances thirst and sweating.</p>	<p><i>Snigdha</i>(unctuous) responsible for mucus accumulation. <i>Guru</i>(heavy) causes heaviness in the body. <i>Picchila</i>(sticky) does sluggish digestion. <i>Manda</i>(weak) causes dull pain.</p>	<p><i>Ushna</i>(hot) causes burning sensation <i>Sara</i>(flow) leads to menstrual irregularities. <i>Teekshna</i>(sharp) causes abdominal pain.</p>

Table No 2: Understanding the Gunas involved in Gulma Nidana.

Type of Gulma	Predominant Nidana	Gunas involved
<i>Vataja Gulma</i>	<p><i>Vatala Ahara</i> Excessive cold exposure <i>Vamana/Virechana</i> without <i>Snehana</i> Emaciation due to fever, diarrhoea, etc.</p>	<p><i>Ruksha</i> (dry) <i>Laghu</i> (light) <i>Sheeta</i> (cold) <i>Khara</i> (rough) <i>Vishada</i> (non-slimy)</p>
<i>Pittaja Gulma</i>	<p>Intake of <i>Ushna, Amla, Lavana, Katu, Madya, Kshara</i>. Exposure to sun Suppression of urges Frequent meals without digestion</p>	<p><i>Ushna</i> (hot) <i>Tikshna</i> (sharp) <i>Drava</i> (liquid) <i>Rooksha</i> (dry) <i>Amla</i> (sour)</p>
<i>Kaphaja Gulma</i>	<p>Intake of heavy, unctuous, sweet, cold foods, <i>Anupa Mamsa</i>. Excess water intake without hunger Suppression of urges Inactivity and irregular posture <i>Vishama Vyayama</i></p>	<p><i>Guru</i> (heavy) <i>Snigdha</i> (unctuous) <i>Sheeta</i> (cold) <i>Sthira</i> (static) <i>Manda</i> (slow) <i>Picchila</i> (slimy)</p>

Table No 3: Understanding the Gunas involved in Gulma Lakshana and Chikitsa.

Gulma symptoms and Gunas involved	Treatment approach (Gunas to be used)	Examples of Ayurvedic treatment
Severe pain (<i>Ruksha, Khara, Sheeta</i>)	<i>Snigdha, Mridu, Ushna</i>	<i>Snehana (Ghrita, Taila), Swedana</i> (hot fomentation), <i>Raktamokshana</i>
Hard Lump (<i>Katinata</i> due to <i>Ruksha, Guru</i>)	<i>Snigdha, Mridu, Picchila</i>	<i>Ghrita prayoga, Snehana, Swedana</i>
Constipation & Obstruction (<i>Suksma, Vishada</i>)	<i>Snigdha, Sara, Drava</i>	<i>Snehana, Swedana, Brimhana</i>
Flatulence, Abdominal Distension (<i>Laghu,</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha, Ushna</i>	<i>Shunthi, Hingu, Pippali, Ajwain</i>

<i>Ruksha, Vishada</i>)		
Heaviness due to <i>Kapha</i> involvement (<i>Guru, Sthira, Picchila, Sheeta</i>)	<i>Laghu, Sara, Drava, Ushna</i>	<i>Langhana, Vamana, Basti</i> , use of <i>Ushna dravya</i> like <i>Trikatu, Agni-Deepana</i> herbs

CONCLUSION

In *Gulma Chikitsa*, *Guna Siddhanta* serves as the foundational principle in selecting treatment modalities. By understanding the *Gulma's* predominant *Guṇas* (primarily *Vata Pradhana*), therapies involving *Snigdha, Mridu, Picchila*, and *Ushna* qualities are preferred to restore balance. *Snehapana, Swedana, Deepana, Anulomana*, and *Vatahara dravyas* are commonly used interventions based on these principles.

Ghrita prayoga is an essential therapeutic approach in *Gulma Chikitsa* due to its digestive, detoxifying, and rejuvenating properties. It not only balances *Vata* and *Pitta doshas*, but also reduces inflammation, improves digestion, and supports tissue repair. Selection of the appropriate medicated ghee depends on the specific type of *Gulma* and the patient's constitution (*Prakriti*).

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